

Corrected measurement: $d_{cor} = (\alpha_{max} - \alpha_{min}) * R_{ear}$

With: R_{ear} = ear radius, $\alpha_{max} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d_{max}}{R_{ear}} \right)$ and $\alpha_{min} = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{d_{min}}{R_{ear}} \right)$